

Identifying Key Hand Joints in Grasping Tasks for Wearable Applications*

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Abstract— Wearable robots have been used for the rehabilitation and assistance of people with reduced hand mobility, such as stroke and spinal cord injury survivors. Most of these devices rely on hand kinematic information to close the control loops. However, the biomechanical complexity of the hand makes kinematics data acquisition and processing an open challenge. To tackle this, we present a method to identify the most informative joints of the hand with respect to hand global posture. We processed kinematics data belonging to two public databases, gathered during the execution of grasping tasks of activities of daily living (ADLs). To carry the analysis, we employed principal component analysis (PCA), standard deviation (SD), and covariance matrix (CvM). Our results suggest that flexion/extension motions of the metacarpal joint of the ring finger bring the most informative content during grasping tasks, whilst abduction/adduction motions are the least relevant. The proposed method represents a simple yet powerful tool for the strategic identification of the most informative joints involved in grasping tasks, which can be used for minimizing the number of sensors and optimizing their placement in wearable hand robots, by generalizing the available information and reducing kinematic redundancy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Partial or complete loss of hand mobility, either following spinal cord injury (SCI), stroke, or other neurological disorders, profoundly limits the performance of Activities of Daily Living (ADLs), negatively impacting the quality of life of the survivors [1], [2]. In recent years, the use of robotic devices has allowed the development of alternative rehabilitation and/or assistance strategies of individuals with neuromotor impairments [3], [4]. In this context, we witnessed the rise of powered exoskeletons, such as robotic gloves that can assist during grasping tasks and promote neurorehabilitation [5], [6]. These devices, however, require to accurately measure the kinematics of the hand in real time to close the control loop (and to implement augmented sensory feedback strategies) [2],[3], [7].

It is well known that the hand is a complex biomechanical system: with 15 joints and about 20 degrees of freedom, it poses significant challenges for kinematic acquisition [8]. The gold standard to acquire kinematic data is optical tracking; despite its high accuracy, this device may be subject to occlusions (especially when tracking fingers) [9]. Conversely, data gloves are widely used as a viable alternative to overcome these problems, at the cost of lower accuracy and the risk of

restricting hand dexterity and/or diminishing hand sensations [8], [9].

In this context, data gloves have gained recognition because they allow acquiring kinematic data in real time through the deformation of their flexible sensors produced by finger movements [10]. Their low weight and softness make this technology feasible for use in proximity with the human body [10], [11], [12], [13]. Although we witnessed significant advancements in the design of soft sensors for wearable robotics and the rise of several companies producing data gloves, elaborating these sensors data can be complex because of different anthropometric proportions of the hand and the nonlinearity of the sensors data with respect to the joint angle, often resulting in complex calibration procedures [1], [8], [9],[10].

To address this issue, researchers have focused on investigating upper limb kinematics leveraging data dimensionality reduction techniques to simplify the description of upper limb kinematics. For instance, Bianchi *et al.* [14] and Lenssen *et al.* [15] conducted studies to define synergistic relationships between degrees of freedom of the wrist during the performance activities of daily living to reduce control complexity of wrist prostheses. Masiero *et al.* [16] performed a study by using functional Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to describe trajectories of the wrist, extrapolating patterns of this joint during ADLs aim in gat evaluating pathology/induced discrepancies. Santello *et al.* [8] and Laffranchi *et al.* [17] used PCA to identify synergies in hand postures for prostheses design. Jarque-Bou *et al.* studied hand synergies during grasping tasks using instrumented gloves for kinematic monitoring [9], [18], [19],[20]. Furthermore, Alicea *et al.* presented the design of an underactuated robotic glove exploiting hand postural synergies to perform a variety of grasps with a single actuator [12].

Although previous studies have already identified hand synergies for grasping motions, it should be noted that the kinematic analysis of individual hand joints is still an open challenge for the scientific community [8], [15]. Due to the complexity of gathering extensive databases involving numerous participants performing various hand movements, many literature studies tend to focus on analyzing smaller populations and/or a restricted range of movements [8], [9],[12], [17], [21]. In addition, the literature often reports an acquisition method in conjunction with PCA evaluation as a

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tool to extract synergies. In this context, other methods together with more extensive databases and from more different sources of information (i.e. instrumented glove and optical tracking) could provide relevant hand information and to complement previous results [8], [9], [12], [17], [21]. It should be noted that deepening the kinematic analysis of the hand can open possibilities for improvements in the development of sensors/actuators for hand rehabilitation/assistive devices, decreasing weight and bulk, and improving usability and wearability.

The objective of this work is to analyze large databases of human hand movements collected during ADLs to identify the joints that bring the most informative content regarding the global shape of the hand in a consistent way. To this aim, we used two public databases including kinematic data of the hand joints collected during the execution of grasping movements, which were acquired using, respectively, an instrumented glove and an optical tracker system [19], [21]. To increase consistency and expand the results of the state of the art, we employed different algorithms to quantify and weight each joint data and identify the individual joints that carry the largest amount of information. In total, data from 84 individuals performing 36 grasping tasks were used. The outcomes of this study may be of interest for minimizing the number of kinematic sensors located on the hand, optimizing their positioning, and therefore reducing computational complexity, which could drastically simplify the design and control of wearable hand robots.

II. METHODOLOGY

To perform a kinematic analysis of the hand during the execution of different grasping movements, two public databases were used. We pre-processed these data before feeding them to three different feature-extraction algorithms. Finally, we compared the outcomes of these algorithms (Fig. 1). In the remaining of this section, we will provide details of this procedure.

A. Public Databases

The two databases contain kinematic signals (i.e., angular data) of the joints of the right hand of healthy subjects, collected during the execution of different ADLs. The first database was built acquiring data with reflective markers, and the second was built acquiring data with a data glove instrumented with 22 bend sensors. More information on these databases is provided below.

1) Database I:

This database contributed to the Hand Corpus Database (The Hand Embodied EU Project) [21]. In this database, kinematic data from 7 healthy participants were stored, recorded using a Vicon MX3+ (Vicon Motion Systems Ltd, UK) optical tracking system and 20 passive reflective markers

at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz. Each participant performed 23 ADL-related movements involving the manipulation of real objects.

2) Database II:

This database was built with kinematic data of 77 participants who performed 40 different movements wearing the Cyberglove II (CyberGlove Systems LLC, USA) [19], which consists of a data glove that collects kinematic information from 22 flexible sensors located on the hand at a sampling rate of 2kHz.

B. Data pre-processing

To compare the two databases, we selected the same kinematic channels, i.e., the angular data of Carpometacarpal (CMC), Metacarpophalangeal (MCP), Interphalangeal (IP), Proximal Interphalangeal (PIP), Distal Interphalangeal (DIP) joints. We then attached a number to each joint, starting from 1 which corresponds to the thumb, and up to 5 which is the little finger. Some joints have multiple degrees of freedom; therefore, those joints are reported with the letter A if we refer to Abduction/Adduction and F if we refer to Flexion/Extension after an underscore character. We excluded the abduction/adduction of MCP2 and MCP5 due to noise issues, resulting in a total of 18 channels.

Subsequently, we resampled the data of each movement to 100 samples to standardize the execution times so that each repetition cycle is in the range [0-100] %. Then, we filtered the data with a 2nd order Butterworth low-pass filter at 5 Hz [20]. Since the experimental protocols used to build the two databases were different, we selected similar Grasping Tasks (GT) in both databases to compare the data. Table I summarizes the selected GTs. Note that Database II includes interactions with imaginary objects, which were excluded in our analysis.

C. Kinematic Analysis

To perform the kinematic analysis, we employed three methods commonly reported in the literature: PCA, Standard Deviation (SD), and Covariance Matrix (CvM). We aimed at comparing these methods to find whether they produce consistent indication of the channel(s) with the largest informative content of the different grasping tasks. For clarity, we briefly describe them in the following paragraphs.

1. PCA is an algorithm that transforms the original data into a set of linearly independent data vectors along various dimensions through a linear transformation, which can be used to extract the main feature components of the data. PCA is often used for the dimensional reduction of high dimensional data and has been previously used for synergy identification [8], [19], [21]. In our case, the weights of the first principal component were used to identify the

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the methodology used to evaluate the kinematic signals of the hand joints during grasping movements.

TABLE I. SELECTED HAND MOVEMENTS BASED ON GRASPING TASKS

Grasping Tasks (GT)	Database I	Database II
GT1	Apple	Sphere
GT2	Bottle	Bottle
GT3	Chalk	Prismatic four fingers grasp
GT4	Cigarette	Index and middle extension
GT5	Comb	Stick
GT6	CD	CD
GT7	Dictionary	Parallel extension
GT8	Egg	Three finger sphere
GT9	Frisbee	Extension type
GT10	Bulb	Quadpod
GT11	Umbrella	Ring
GT12	Toothpick	Tip pinch
GT13	Toothbrush	Screwdriver
GT14	Mug	Fixed hook
GT15	Bottle cap	Bottle cap
GT16	Cherry	Prismatic pinch

channels that represent the largest amount of variance explained [19],[21]. It should be noted that the principal component score scan varies between [-1,1], where -1 and 1 correspond to a large influence, either negative or positive, while 0 represents no influence. Based on the above, we computed the absolute value of the weights, where 1 represents a large influence of the channels on the principal, while 0 represents no

Algorithm 1 PCA Algorithm

Input: $X \in R^{M \times k}$ ▶ Let X be the vector of pre-processed data corresponding to the kinematics of all participants during the performance of each of the movements, M the total number of samples, and k the number of channels

Output: PC and w ▶ Principal components and weight matrix

1: $X_{norm} = \frac{X - \text{mean}(X)}{\text{std}(X)}$ ▶ Normalization

2: $PC = \text{pca}(X_{norm})$ ▶ Obtaining the PC matrix

3: $L = \text{abs}(PC(:,1))$ ▶ Computing the absolute value for the first PC

influence. This procedure is explained in detail in Algorithm 1.

- SD is a statistical measure that quantifies the dispersion of a database with respect to its arithmetic mean. This metric is used to assess the variability of signals and can provide crucial information for evaluating data fluctuations during different states and pattern recognition [22]. The channels with larger standard deviation during movement execution

$$SD_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M (X_{ij} - \mu_j)^2}, \quad (1)$$

correspond to wider joints excursions. SD is calculated as follows (Eq. 1).

where M is the number of samples, k is the number of channels, μ is the mean of channel j , and SD is the standard deviation of channel j . Finally, the outputs were normalized using min-max normalization to allow a comparison between data.

- Covariance Matrix (CvM) is a statistical tool that describes the variability and the linear relationships between multiple variables [23]. Therefore, CvM provides important information about possible

Algorithm 2 CvM Algorithm

Input: $X \in R^{M \times k}$ ▶ Let X be the vector of pre-processed data corresponding to the kinematics of all participants during the performance of each of the movements, M the total number of samples, and k the number of channels

Output: C and F ▶ CvM and Features (F) for each channel

1: $\mu = \text{mean}(X)$

2: $C = \frac{1}{M-1} \sum_{i=1}^M (X_i - \mu)^T (X_i - \mu)^T$

3: $f = C(:,1)$ ▶ The first CvM component

4: $F = \text{normalize}(f)$ ▶ Min-max normalization

patterns in the channels during the execution of each movement. This is essential for understanding motor coordination (synergies). The procedure is described in more detail in Algorithm 2 [24].

D. Evaluation

To assess the consistency and comparability of the two databases, we calculated the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (CC) among the performance metrics using Eq.2.

$$CC = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (U_i - \bar{U})(V_i - \bar{V})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (U_i - \bar{U})^2 (V_i - \bar{V})^2}}, \quad (2)$$

where i is each point of the U and V vectors, n is the total of points, and U and V are the performance metrics (i.e., PCA, SD, and CvM scores) of databases I and II, respectively. Scores close to [-1,1] indicate correlations between the evaluated data (negative or positive), whereas scores close to zero indicate that there is no linear relationship between the variables [25]. In addition, CC is calculated among each movement to evaluate the similarity of the joint angles during the execution of different grasps. In this last, U and V in Eq.2 are the kinematic data during the execution of two movements (Table I), an example could be CC between GT1 and GT1 for database I, for database II, among databases, and so on.

Fig.2. Metrics calculated for each channel and each method for (a) database I and (b) Database II. **Note:** _F for flexion/extension, _A for abduction/adduction, 1 to 5 for each finger, where 1 is the tumble up to 5 that is the little.

III. RESULTS

From the first database, we observed that the highest scores were obtained by PIP4, MCP5_F and MCP2_F with PCA, SD, and CvM, respectively (Fig.2a). Conversely, the lowest scores were obtained by channels MCP4_A, (PCA) MCP1_F (SD), and CMC1_F (CvM). On the other hand, from the second database we observed that the highest scores were obtained by DIP5 (PCA) and DIP4 (SD and CvM), whereas the lowest scores were obtained by CMC1_F (PCA, SD, CvM) (Fig.2b).

By observing the heat maps of each channel, we can grasp a better understanding of our results (Fig. 3). We can observe that channels MCP3_F, PIP3, PIP4 and MCP5 obtained the highest scores for database I (Fig.3a-c), whereas the channels DIP3, PIP4, DIP4 and MCP5 obtained the largest scores for database II (Fig.3d-f). The channels that provided the least amount of information corresponded to CMC1_A, MCP3_F, and MCP4_A for both databases, which are related to abduction/adduction motions. The channels associated to flexion/extension that produced the lowest scores are DIP2, DIP4, and PIP5 for database I and CMC1_F, DIP2, and PIP5 for database II. In addition, the CCs scores were used to

compare the two databases to identify coherence among the channels. The outcomes were 0.71 (PCA), 0.68 (SD), and 0.58 (CvM).

From the comparison of the individual movements of the two databases using CC scores, we could observe patterns in the variation of the channels during the execution of different movements. E.g., GT3 and GT8, GT9 and GT2, GT10 and GT2, GT12 and GT16, and GT13 and GT15 for database I with $CC > 0.95$ (Fig.4a). On the other hand, we can observe the strong similarity between GT2 and GT14, GT4 vs GT12, GT5 and GT8, GT9, and GT10 movements, with $CC > 0.95$ scores (Fig.4b). Finally, we can observe correlations across the two databases, highlighting GT5 and GT8, GT5 and GT9, GT5 and GT10, GT13, and GT8, GT14, and GT8, with $CC > 0.5$ (Fig.4c). Specifically, these outcomes may be referenced to identify similar movements involved in ADLs. E.g., in database I the pairs of movements that reported the largest similarity are the GTs of Chalk and EGG, Frisbee and Bottle, Bulb and Bottle, Toothpick and Cherry, and Toothbrush and Bottle cap (Fig4a). For database II, the GTs with the highest correlation scores were the Bottle and Fixed Hook, Index-Middle and Extension Tip pinch, stick and three-finger sphere,

Fig.3. Heat map of hand angles during the execution of grasping tasks: (a) PCA with Database I, (b) SD with Database I, (c) CvM with Database II, (d) PCA with Database II, (e) SD with Database II, and (f) CvM with Database II. (g) Anatomical joint location for both databases. **Note:** _F stands for flexion/extension, _A for abduction/adduction, 1 to 5 refer to each finger, where 1 is the thumb and 5 is the little finger.

Fig.4. CC for each GT (Table I) compared one vs one of (a) Database I, (b) Database II and (c) Database I vs Database II.

and three fingers here and quadpod (Fig.4b). Additionally, the movements with the highest similitude among the database correspond to Comb and Three-finger sphere, Comb and Extension type, Comb and Quadpod, Toothbrush and three fingers here, and Mug and three-finger sphere (Fig.4c).

IV. DISCUSSION

From our results, we can infer that there is an important, yet unexpected, contribution of the ring finger during the execution of grasping tasks. In addition, our findings show low influence of the CMC1_F, MCP_3A and MCP_4A channels (i.e., abduction/adduction). Moreover, DIP2 and PIP5 bring the lowest amount of information related to flexion/extension motion, which allow to infer a scarce contribution of this joints during grasping tasks. It is also possible to observe the coordinated motions of middle and ring fingers in grasping movements of both databases. The large CC (0.71) highlights the coherence of these results among the databases.

It is worth noting that the contact forces between the fingers and the objects induced deformations in the hand posture with respect to hand motions in the free space. For this reason, the movements captured in different experimental protocols may affect the scores among databases (PCA, SD and CvM). For this reason, we used CC to associate similar movements. These results allowed the identification of similar behaviors during different the execution of grasping tasks involved in ADLs, which can be useful to devise sensing systems for wearable robots for the hand.

In fact, it is possible to identify key joints of the hand that are primarily involved in grasping tasks and tracking these joints may lead to relevant information. On the other hand, channels with low scores may be associated to anatomical points that do not provide relevant information or are redundant, i.e., tracking these joints is less relevant. Our results agree with previous studies. For example, Jarque-Bou *et al.* performed a study in which PCA results determined the synergies between IP1_F, MCP1_F, CMC1_A, PIP2_F, MCP4_F, and PIP4_F [9]. In addition, they found synergies between the flexion of the MCP joints of fingers 3 to 5 using PCA in 20 movements executed by 77 individuals [17]. Our study aimed to extend this knowledge using two databases, performing both consolidated analysis (PCA) and less explored methods (SD and CvM) [22], [23], [24].

Previous studies have reported the identification of synergies through PCA during the execution of grasping tasks

with smaller population sizes and fewer hand movements. For instance, Laffranchi *et al.* used the first principal component to model a hand prosthesis using data from six individuals and nine object grasping tasks, where synergies related to flexion of MCP were found [17]. Gracia-Ibáñez *et al.* [24] extracted synergies through PCA from 24 individuals during the execution of 24 ADLs finding synergies specifically among PIP and MCP5 with the first principal component. Jarque-Bou *et al.* [9] recently presented a similar study with 27 individuals and 20 movements identifying synergies among IP1_F, MCP1_F, MCP4_F, CMC1_F, CMC1_A, and PIP2, and PIP4. Alicea *et al.* used dimensionality reduction techniques to implement a robotic rehabilitation glove with a patient who suffered a spinal cord injury [12]. This study used the information of thumb, index and middle finger in the sagittal plane, which represents the first two components in the PCA. On the other hand, synergy investigations and dimensionality reduction through kinematic information have been performed also in applications not involving grasping tasks. Masiero *et al.* conducted a study on the identifying synergies of the wrist with 13 subjects and 14 movements [16]. Another study by West *et al.* [26] determined synergies by using eigenvectors of the hand joints of an individual playing a piano. Differently from previous literature studies, we performed a kinematic assessment on a larger pool of data. In fact, we processed data from 84 individuals (7 for database I and 77 for database II) and 36 tasks (18 for each database). Moreover, since the two databases we analyzed were built employing different acquisition techniques, we believe that our results can be generalized.

It is worth noting that the identification of channels that provide more information during the execution of grasping tasks allows the development of robust assistive/rehabilitation robotic devices, as demonstrated in previous studies. For instance, Alicea *et al.* [12]. In their work, a synergy-based robotic glove was used by a patient with spinal cord injury to power cylindrical and pinch grasping tasks. Their robotic glove employed strategically placed actuators based on postural synergies to maximize grasping movements while simultaneously reducing control complexity and power transmission. On the other hand, Laffranchi *et al.* [17] developed a prosthesis that replicates the key movements of a healthy hand using as a reference the synergies obtained from the PCA during 9 movements, which allowed for better usability during ADL. These strategies represent significant advances in the field, although we believe that adding more

grasps may further improve the outcomes. To this aim, our results may allow identifying other channels that provide relevant kinematic information. This may have potential use in the reduction of sensors and actuators implemented in robotic devices, encompassing a larger number of grasping tasks involved in ADLs.

Interestingly, our results point towards the importance of middle and ring fingers in grasping tasks, specifically in the MCP_F and PIP joints, while those related to abduction tasks (MCP_A) were less relevant. These results are in line with previous studies where the low variability of the thumb and index finger has been related to their independence, specifically in grasping tasks [9]. Additionally, these findings are directly dependent on the executed movements and do not mean that the other joints do not play a role during grasping tasks, but that during our modeling, the MCP and PIP joints of the ring finger showed more relevance [9]. However, if higher accuracy is required or even evaluation of non-grasping tasks, the joints associated with the index finger and thumb may improve angle estimation during movements. Notably, noisy sensors (MCP2_A and MCP5_A) and the difference in data collection procedures among the two datasets is a limiting factor for our comparison. For future studies, we recommend increasing the sample size and the number of hand movements, including non-grasping tasks, as well as adopting more specific task classification methods to further increase the generalizability of our results.

V. CONCLUSION

This study unveiled a set of hand joints that represent the greatest amount of kinematic information during the execution of grasping tasks in ADLs. The flexion/extension movements of PIP4, MCP2, MCP5, DIP4, and DIP5 joints are the most informative, while the abduction/adduction metacarpals were the least relevant. In addition, we observed that DIP2 and PIP5 bring the least amount of information. With the proposed method, we analyzed the kinematics of the hand with good generalizability of the outcomes thanks to the evaluation of two distinct databases built using different acquisition setups and different – yet similar – grasping tasks. We aim to expand these results and leverage them for the strategic design of the sensing layer of wearable hand robots for the rehabilitation and assistance of people with neuromotor impairments.

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